

Surface modification of WE43 magnesium alloy via alkali/stearic acid treatment for biodegradable drug-eluting stent applications

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HIGHLIGHTS

- The anodic layer decreased the hydrogen formation and degradation rate of WE43.
- The anodic layer type, roughness, and thickness influence its corrosion behaviour.
- Stearic acid coatings were fabricated using spray coating and dip coating methods.
- Stearic acid coating makes the surface hydrophobic against degradation.
- Modified WE43 can maintain drug/gene carrier layers for stent applications.

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ABSTRACT

WE43 is a biodegradable magnesium alloy with a high potential for cardiovascular stent applications. Although it has many adequate properties, there are barriers to using it as a drug-eluting stent vehicle. Corrosion and hydrogen gas formation have an adverse effect on the surface, causing attached drug carriers to separate, which limits its functionality as a stent. An alkali treatment in 1 M NaOH solution at various applied potentials was utilized to fix this issue. Subsequently, a stearic acid layer was formed by two different methods to reduce corrosion by decreasing water uptake of the surface. The anodic film's surface morphology and phase structure were analysed using scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS). Nano-indentation tests were carried out to evaluate the anodic layer's mechanical properties. Its corrosion behaviour was characterized using potentiodynamic polarization (PDP), electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) and hydrogen evolution tests. The adhesive, thin yet effective oxide layers achieved in all the potentials showed increased corrosion resistance. It significantly decreased hydrogen formation, which were then sealed with stearic acid, and the surface became hydrophobic. This sealing layer acted as an additional barrier and enhanced the corrosion resistance of the magnesium alloy up to fifteen times bigger.

1. Introduction

Biodegradable materials for cardiovascular applications are preferable over permanent implants that can cause long-term complications. An ideal biodegradable stent provides mechanical support until the blockage in an artery is gone and then degrades naturally, leaving no irritation, inflammation, or disorder in the human body [1,2]. Magnesium (Mg), famous for being the lightest engineering metal, is the 7th most abundant element in the earth's crust [3]. It is a promising choice

for stent applications as it is biocompatible, and when it degrades in the body, its products are neither harmful nor toxic [4]. However, pure Mg is unsuitable for such applications because of its poor mechanical properties and fast degradation, which leads to structural failure and deterioration [5].

WE43 is a high-strength Mg alloy with excellent corrosion resistance, far superior to most conventional Mg alloys, including AZ91, AM60, AM50, and AZ31. High-performance creep resistance, good corrosion and ignition resistance are properties inherent to rare earth (RE)

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alloying elements [2,6]. Compared with AZ alloys, WE43 has no Al, which has proven to be neurotoxic and can cause dementia and Alzheimer's disease [7,8,35]. WE43 is biodegradable but cannot be used as a bare metal stent since restenosis occurs due to coronary interaction with the stent. However, it can serve as a good platform for anti-proliferative drugs or gene carriers [9,10]. An anodic layer formed by PEO¹/MAO² or alkali treatment can enhance the corrosion behaviour of WE43 [11,12]. Recently, researchers have shown that not only this anodic layer can improve corrosion behaviour, but also it is advantageous to maintain the drug/gene carrier layer or be the platform itself [13,14]. A complete DES³/GES⁴ may eliminate late complications of stent implantation, including in-stent restenosis, simply by degrading without producing any toxic substances, after maintaining luminal integrity during the period of high risk of restenosis in the first 9–12 months [15].

Biodegradable DES/GES may eventually allow the vessel wall to preserve its normal function. In addition, biodegradable stents may eliminate the limitations of permanent DES implants, including long-term endothelial dysfunction, delayed reendothelialization, thrombogenicity, permanent physical irritation and chronic inflammatory local reactions [16]. To achieve this, WE43 can be coated with biocompatible and biodegradable polymers such as PLLA⁵, PCL⁶, PLGA⁷, etc. or a mix of these, allowing for more complex pharmacokinetics. Thrombosis is still one of the major problems in the DES area. Therefore, the biocompatibility of polymers must be considered along with elasticity and drug release properties [17].

Biodegradable polymer coatings on magnesium and its alloys improve the corrosion resistance of implants in the body over the long term and improve the biocompatibility of metallic Mg in biodegradable applications [18]. In multi-layered biodegradable stents, the inner layer would provide structural or adhesion requirements, whereas the outer layer would serve to control the release of various drugs or genes at desired rates [16,19].

The big problem with using magnesium and its alloys as a biodegradable DES/GES platform is that they are susceptible to degradation in any aqueous environment with more than 30 mmol/l chloride content. This means that Mg corrodes in the body where the concentration of chloride is above 150 mmol/l. Magnesium reacts in such aqueous solutions as per Eq (1):

Magnesium hydroxide acts as a protection film in water. Still, when the chloride concentration is high, magnesium hydroxide turns into magnesium chloride, and severe pitting occurs on the surface [20]. According to equation (1), the other concern is the formation of harmful hydrogen gas pockets that would cause any coating to peel or spall away from the substrate surface. This removes the polymer layers from the metallic vehicle, even though they need to remain on the stent after stenting and continue drug release for a sufficient period [21,22].

The formation of hydrogen gas can be reduced by decreasing the corrosion rate of Mg. Alkali treatment is a practical method to form a bioactive, adhesive, corrosion-resistant oxide layer on the surface of Mg alloys [23].

Reaction (2) shows what happens on the surface during alkali passivation. Considering reactions (1) and (2), by having the Mg(OH)₂

on the surface, increasing the content of the reaction products in reaction (1), the reaction equilibrium changes, and the progress of the forward reaction is retarded. This ensures less hydrogen gas pocket formation and better resistance against corrosion [24]. The magnesium oxide formed on the surface is porous and needs secondary treatments to seal it for further control over degradation [25]. Stearic acid [CH₃(CH₂)₁₆COOH] is a long-chain saturated fatty acid, nontoxic, biocompatible and insoluble in aqueous solutions [26]. This hydrophobic material seals the oxide layer and further blocks the contact between the chloride ions and the magnesium alloy substrate [27].

In this work, the WE43 surface was modified to maintain future drug or gene carrier layers. Alkali treatment was performed to lower corrosion and hydrogen formation on the surface by creating a thin adhesive layer. The following applied stearic acid treatment enhanced the adhesion adequately for any polymer layer acting as carrier and decreased the hydrophilicity of the surface. In addition, it acted as an extra protective layer against corrosion. The mentioned modifications can be an advancement towards the manufacturing of biodegradable Mg-based DES/GES as this approach presents a novel strategy on a two-layer coating, anodic and a subsequent sealing layer. This work addresses how to adjust the al-treatment parameters to get desired behaviour from the oxide layer on WE43 and then make it hydrophobic with a good adhesion for polymer coating as carrier to overcome limitations associated with using WE43 as a drug/gene-eluting stent, paving the way for improved functionality and potential advancements in cardiovascular treatment.

2. Materials & method

2.1. Material and sample preparation

Commercial WE43 with 1 mm-thick sheets containing 4% Y, 3.3% RE (Nd, Gd), and 0.5% Zr wt% (bought from Shanghai Metal Products Co., Ltd., China) were used. For the alkali treatment (al-treatment), samples (25mm × 20 mm) were cut out of the sheets. They were polished with sandpaper up to No. 2500, rinsed with distilled water and then dried with an airgun. 1 M NaOH (AppliChem, Germany) alkali solution with pH 13 was used for treatment.

2.2. Al-treatment and electrochemical characterization

To find the best voltage for al-treatment, linear sweep voltammetry (LSV) was performed using a potentiostat/galvanostat CS310 (Wuhan CorrTest Instruments Corp., Ltd., China) on 100 ml of PBS solution that was placed on a hotplate stirrer (Stuart-US152). The stirrer speed was set at 200 rpm, and the temperature was maintained at 25 °C. WE43 samples and platinum sheet with an area of 100 mm² were used as the WE⁸ and CE⁹, respectively. The RE¹⁰ was an Ag/AgCl electrode in saturated KCl. The potentiodynamic polarization curves were measured by sweeping the potential from 9 V to –1 V (vs OCP¹¹) with a scan rate of –100 mV/s three times. Sweeping the potential from positive to negative values proved to help obtain producible results and avoid pitting on the working electrode. After finding the best potential range, al-treatment was performed using OWON DC Power Supply (Fujian Lilliput Optoelectronics Technology Co., Ltd., China). WE43 samples were treated at 4, 5 and 6 V for 10 min with a stainless steel 316 as the cathode. The samples were then immersed in hot water (≈90 °C) for 2 min post-treatment and then dried in the air.

¹ Plasma electrolytic oxidation.

² Micro-arc oxidation.

³ drug-eluting stent.

⁴ Gene-eluting stent.

⁵ poly (L-lactic acid).

⁶ polycaprolactone.

⁷ poly(glycolic-co-lactic-acid).

⁸ working electrode.

⁹ counter electrode.

¹⁰ reference electrode.

¹¹ open circuit potential.

2.3. Stearic acid (SA) treatment

A SA (Sigma-Aldrich, USA) layer was formed on the surface of the 5V samples using ultrasonic atomization spray-coating and dip-coating methods. A 0.1 mol/l SA in ethanol (Fisher Scientific International, Inc) solution was used for both methods. Spray coating was performed using a LULP500 ultrasonic liquid processor (Cheersonic Ultrasonic Co.) for 20 cycles with a 10 cm distance between the nozzle and the sample. For the dip coating, samples were immersed in the solution for 2 h. In both methods, samples were dried in the incubator at 50 °C for 2 h.

2.4. Surface characterization

Microstructural analysis was performed using a field-emission scanning electron microscope (Zeiss Sigma 300), and a Hitachi Topdesk 4000 was used for EDS analysis to characterize the layers formed on the surface. X-ray diffractometry (Inel- EQUINOX3000) was utilized to seek different phases in al-treated samples using monochromatic Cu-K radiation. 200 g/l CrO₃ (Sigma-Aldrich, USA) in demineralized water was used to remove the corrosion products from the samples to investigate corroded surfaces. Cross-sectional images were taken to measure the oxide layer thickness. The chemical composition of the corrosion products on the surface was investigated by X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS, Kratos Axis Ultra DLD, USA) using an X-ray source of Al K α (1486.6 eV) with an elliptical spot size of 300 μ \times 700 μ . Roughness parameters were measured using the Mitutoyo SJ-410 surface roughness tester. Each parameter was measured five times, and the average was reported. The contact angle was measured using an Ossila contact angle goniometer with 10 μ l water droplets. The mechanical properties of the anodic layer were measured using the nanoindentation test (Bruker Hysitron TI Premier Nanoindenter, USA) along with Oliver-Pharr's method. Twenty tests per sample were performed spaced by 20 μ m, and nanoindentation was loaded up to 14000 μ N.

2.5. Hydrogen formation and corrosion measurement

The hydrogen evolution rate was measured using a customized setup where WE43 samples with an exposed area of 10 mm² were put in a beaker containing 100 ml of PBS¹² (Fisher Scientific International, Inc). A funnel was placed over the specimen to ensure all the hydrogen gas evolved from the surface of the sample was collected. A burette was mounted over the funnel and was initially full of the test solution. The hydrogen collected by the funnel went into the burette and gradually displaced the test solution. In this way, the volume of the evolved hydrogen was measured by reading the position of the test solution level in the burette [28].

Electrochemical tests were performed in PBS using the mentioned CorrTest CS310 electrochemical interface. Before the EIS¹³ and PDP¹⁴ measurements, the samples were immersed in PBS for 2 h to gain a steady open circuit potential (E_{oc}). Then, the electrode potential was scanned from +0.5 to -0.5 V versus the E_{oc} at a scan rate of 2 mV/s. CS Studio 6 software was used with the least squares method to fit the polarization curves obtained from the patterns. EIS tests were performed in the frequency range from 100 kHz to 10 mHz, and the perturbation amplitude was 10 mV. The obtained experimental data were fitted with Zview software.

Fig. 1. Polarization curve for WE43 versus Ag/AgCl electrode in 1 M NaOH obtained by LSV.

Fig. 2. Current vs time curves achieved for different potentials.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Anodic layer

3.1.1. Formation stages

Fig. 1 shows the polarization curve obtained by LSV. There was a current peak between the anode and cathode in the potential range of 4–6 V, where the extent of oxidation on the surface was maximum. No significant oxide layer formed on the surface below 2.5 V or in the range of 6–8 V. Also, oxidation above 8 V led to large pits, which was undesirable. The extent of oxidation is directly related to electrical power as indicated in equation (3), where power, $P(W)$, is equal to potential, $E(V)$, multiplied by current, $I(A)$. Thus, higher power ensures more dissolution of Mg and a faster rate of oxide layer formation. Therefore, 4–6 V was regarded as the best applicable potential range for al-treatment in 1 M NaOH.

$$P = E \times I \quad (3)$$

Fig. 2 illustrates current transients for WE43 in 1 M NaOH. With the

¹² Phosphate Buffered Saline.

¹³ electrochemical impedance spectroscopy.

¹⁴ potentiodynamic polarization.

Table 1
Current achieved for WE43 samples in different potentials.

Voltage (V)	Max Current achieved in 10 min (A)	Time to reach the max current stage (s)
4	0.06	<250
5	0.27	<120
6	0.53	<60

progress of time, the current density increased due to reaction (4), the dissolution of magnesium, which reacts with OH^- ions, forming $\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2$ in reaction (5). The current density reached its maximum value and then remained constant until the end of the treatment. This is due to the stationary state of dissolution and film formation. At 6V, the dissolution rate of Mg is higher than the formation of the oxide film, which is why after 10 min, there was a slightly positive slope, and no stationary state was observed as the current did not become constant.

According to Table 1, the maximum constant current was achieved faster at higher applied voltages. According to equation (6), potential, E (V), equals current, I (A), multiplied by resistance, R (Ω). So, a higher applied potential between the anode and cathode leads to a higher current when the resistance of the alkali solution is almost constant. A higher current has more power to dissolve and turn Mg into oxide. Lower currents need more time to dissolve the same amount of Mg and reach the stationary state of dissolution and film formation, so they can only influence a thin layer of the Mg substrate, ending in a thin anodic layer.

$$E = I \times R \quad (6)$$

The stages of anodic layer formation on WE43 and optical microscopic images are shown in Fig. 3. At low potentials, most of the extent of the anodic layer is compact, called the barrier layer. With increasing time and potential, a porous layer forms and grows on the barrier layer. For WE43, the porous layer refers to a layer rougher than the barrier layer with pores that are not similar in size or pattern, which is seen for the oxide layer on the aluminium.

3.1.2. Surface characteristics

Cross-section images in Fig. 4 show that the anodic layer for the treated sample at 4 V differs from 5V to 6V samples and is thinner. This is because it mainly consists of a barrier-type oxide layer. With increasing the voltage, more porosity is seen, and the oxide surface is uneven as it is the porous oxide layer. Higher voltages increase the thickness of the anodic layer due to the greater power of dissolution and formation. The thin barrier layer with low porosity in Fig. 4(b) is not observed in Fig. 4 (c) for the 6V sample. It is because the porous layer grows in both upward and downward directions, and the barrier layer shrinks and is not visible for the 6V sample. This is because the formation of the anodic layer differs from when a substance is deposited on the surface and increases the thickness of the sample. Instead, it is a conversion coating whereby magnesium and any layer with a concentration of Mg can be converted into a porous oxide layer. Despite al-treatment at 4V, the colour of the alkaline solution changed from neutral to grey at 5 and 6 V as the extent of Mg dissolution in NaOH was relatively high.

The XRD patterns of different al-treated samples are shown in Fig. 5. The phase composition of the anodic coatings mainly consisted of the peaks of Mg (Ref. Code: 96-901-3240) and MgO (Ref. Code: 96-901-

Fig. 3. Anodic layer formation stages on WE43 in 1 M NaOH at 4–6 V.

Fig. 4. Cross-section image of samples al-treated in a) 4 V, b) 5 V, and c) 6 V with an average thickness of the formed anodic layer and d) 4 V, e) 5 V, and f) 6 V with higher magnification with EDS map.

3060). As the anodic layer thickness is low, the Mg from the substrate is also detected, where porosity and thickness have affected the peak intensity of Mg.

As shown in Fig. 6, the anodic coating is formed on the surface layer by layer. EDS results show that the Mg/O ratio decreased from 1.47 for the 4V sample to 1.22 for 5V and then to 1.12 for 6V. The significant difference between 4V compared to the 5V and 6V samples is due to the different types of the oxide layer and the extent of oxidation at the higher voltages. Al and Si are present due to contamination as the EDS is gained from the oxide layer and does not show the alloying elements. According to Table 2, Ra values indicate that the roughness has increased with increasing the potential. This is because more magnesium was dissolved, leaving the surface with cavities and pores, which at the same time was being partially replaced with oxides. The anodic layer on the 4V sample is mostly barrier type which is smoother than other

samples. For 5V and 6V samples, higher Mg dissolution and oxide formation lead to a rougher surface with random pores and peaks. That is the reason R_p and R_v are higher at more applied potentials. Fig. 7 illustrates the growth of the anodic layer over time and the oxides that are formed layer by layer and increase the roughness.

3.1.3. Mechanical properties of the anodic layer

Fig. 8 shows the load associated with the depth of the WE43 before and after al-treatment. The maximum depth under approximately 14000 μN is about 1000 nm (1 μm) for the WE43, while al-treated samples have similar depth with less load, which is 600, 2500, and 5100 μN for 4V, 5V and 6V samples, respectively. Load-depth diagram was used to calculate the micro-hardness and elastic modulus of different samples. The anodic layer did not have constant mechanical values; therefore, micro-hardness and elastic modulus were measured

Fig. 5. XRD patterns for different Al-treated samples.

twenty times on each sample, and the average is reported in Table 3. It is shown that hardness, elasticity and stiffness have increased by increasing the time of the Al-treatment. As seen in Fig. 6, the oxides extent is increased in the anodic layer by increasing the oxidation time,

which is the reason for higher hardness for longer oxidation times. Also, more oxides mean more ceramic-like behaviour, which is why the modulus and stiffness of the barrier-type anodic layer (4V) are lower than that of the porous anodic layer formed on 5V and 6V samples. The elasticity of anodic layer ranging from 8 to 12 GPa is 4–5 times lower than the elasticity of WE43 but similar to biodegradable polymers that are common for stent coating. This is desirable to ensure that the multi-layered coating has uniform mechanical properties.

3.1.4. Corrosion behaviour of the anodic layer

Fig. 9 shows the potentiodynamic polarization curves obtained from Al-treated samples at different applied potentials. According to the fitting results (Table 4), Al-treatment decreases the corrosion current, which means the anodic layer acts as a barrier to protect the Mg substrate. This is because it is like an insulator and does not conduct electricity. Samples treated at 4 and 5 V have a lower corrosion current. For the 4V sample, the thin anodic layer has lower roughness. Thus, less water absorption leads to less corrosion. Al-treatment at 4V and 5V have shifted the corrosion potential toward positive and passive values, but

Table 2

Roughness parameters were measured for Al-treated samples.

Sample	R_a (μm)	R_p (μm)	R_v (μm)	R_z (μm)
4V	0.4 ± 0.1	1.6 ± 0.2	2.6 ± 0.2	3.5 ± 0.4
5V	0.7 ± 0.1	3.6 ± 0.2	2.6 ± 0.2	4.7 ± 0.4
6V	1.7 ± 0.1	8.8 ± 0.2	7.2 ± 0.2	14.2 ± 0.4

Fig. 6. SEM images and EDS analysis of the surface of a) 4V, b) 5V, and c) 6V samples.

Fig. 7. The microstructure of the anodic layer formed at 6 V after a) 1 min, b) 5 min, and c) 10 min.

Fig. 8. Nanoindentation load/unload-depth curves for WE43 before and after al-treatment.

Table 3

Mechanical properties of WE43 before and after al-treatment obtained via nanoindentation.

Sample	Hardness (GPa)	Modulus (GPa)	Stiffness ($\mu\text{N}/\text{nm}$)
WE43	1.02	45.93	166.54
4V	0.11	7.89	56.69
5V	0.14	11.78	67.48
6V	0.15	12.25	84.34

for the 6V sample, the corrosion potential is shifted toward negative and active values. Thus, although the type of the anodic layer can determine the corrosion potential, excess porosity has increased the corrosion current of the sample. The potentiodynamic polarization tests were performed after 2 h of immersion, and these findings are considered early-stage results as corrosion behaviour changes over time.

The Nyquist plot in Fig. 10 and the results of the fitting of the experimental data shown in Table 5 reveal the presence of two capacitive loops from high to low frequencies for all samples. The plots can be explained by the equivalent circuits (ECs) in Fig. 10(c), where R_s represents the solution resistance and CPE_o and R_o represent the capacity and resistance of the anodic layer. CPE_{dl} and R_{ct} determined the double-layer capacitance and charge transfer resistance, respectively. EC(1) illustrates the plot for the 5V sample where two capacitances regarding the metal and anodic layer are connected in parallel. EC(2) represents the plots for 4V and 6V samples where two capacitances are connected in series. This means there are two distinct surfaces; metal and anodic layer, which for the 4V sample is barrier type and for the 6V sample is porous. This difference between 4V and 6V samples compared to 5V

Fig. 9. Potentiodynamic polarization curves of WE43 and different al-treated samples versus Ag/AgCl electrode immersed in PBS solution.

Table 4

The fitting results of polarization curves obtained from WE43 and al-treated samples in PBS solution.

Sample	E_{corr} (mV)	I_{corr} (μA)	β_a (mV)	$-\beta_c$ (mV)
4V	-1.52	56.19	40.9	188.5
5V	-1.52	55.44	39.0	260.3
6V	-1.53	71.70	39.8	292.5
WE43	-1.53	131.17	84.8	214.3

sample is also visible in the Bode plot in low frequencies. High dissolution of Mg at 6V increases the size of pores, giving access to the solution to reach the WE43 surface and decreasing the resistance. The Bode plot shows that the overall corrosion resistance is bigger for the barrier oxide layer formed at 4V and the 5V sample with controlled pore size. Less pore size means less roughness, and as long as rough surfaces have a larger interfacial area, any increase in surface roughness is expected to increase the corrosion rate [29]. In longer times, pitting on the surface can change the resistance of the anodic layer.

Fig. 11(a) shows the OCP for different samples immersed in PBS versus time. This equilibrium potential is measured while the circuit is open, meaning no current flows and no external voltage is applied. Therefore, the OCP depicts the real corrosion behaviour of the samples. There is a sharp decrease in the early stage because of the destruction of the naturally formed passive layer on the surface. Then, there is an increase for all the samples, which is sharper for the al-treated samples than the untreated WE43. The increase in OCP can be related to forming of a layer of corrosion products with protective properties that thicken

Fig. 10. a) Nyquist, b) Bode plots and c) equivalent circuits for different al-treated samples immersed in PBS solution.

Table 5

Parameters determined from Nyquist plot fitting for al-treated samples.

Sample	R_s (Ω cm 2)	R_1 (Ω cm 2)	CPE_o -T ($S^n \cdot Q^{-1} \cdot cm^{-2}$)	n_o	R_{ct} (Ω cm 2)	CPE_{dl} -T ($S^n \cdot Q^{-1} \cdot cm^{-2}$)	n_{dl}
4V	94.74	11200	5.2E-6	0.86	6706	2.2E-4	0.85
5V	92.26	6539	7.1E-6	0.97	8209	1.0E-4	0.58
6V	91.16	3845	8.2E-6	0.96	5248	2.1E-4	0.56

over time. It can be said that, after 48 h, an equilibrium has been reached for the al-treated samples where the deviation of the OCP does not exceed 0.05 V. This is due to the surface coverage of the anodic layer and corrosion products together, while this is not observed for the WE43 sample with the OCP still increasing after 144 h. The OCP difference between samples indicates the higher degree of passivation for the surface of al-treated samples. High fluctuations for the 4V sample are because of the localized pits in the thin barrier layer, where there is a potential difference between the thin anodic layer and the WE43 surface.

The cumulative hydrogen gas produced on the surface is shown in Fig. 11(b), which is in accordance with Fig. 11(a). There was a sharp rise in the first 24 h for all samples. This is due to the low OCP of samples in the first 24 h and the corrosion that happens on the surface. The OCP for the al-treated samples started to increase no later than 2 h of immersion, but for the WE43 sample, the increase began after 6 h of immersion. This explains the higher hydrogen formation of the WE43 sample as the passivation started earlier for the al-treated samples. This means that the anodic layer help maintain the surface by decreasing the exposure time to the PBS solution, as PBS products sit faster on the anodic layer. This is due to hydrophilicity and the roughness of the anodic layer leading to less hydrogen formation.

For the WE43 sample, there was a sharp increase, followed by a gradual increase. For the 4V sample, the hydrogen production rate decreased after 24 h, but the extent of hydrogen continued to increase and did not reach a steady state even after 144 h. According to the EIS results, the 4V sample showed better corrosion resistance but was associated with more hydrogen production. The reason for this is that the PDP tests were done after 2 h of immersion, while in longer times, the barrier oxide layer started to pit, and hydrogen production increased. The porous oxide layer on the 6V sample allows the solution to reach the substrate/electrolyte interface, and thus hydrogen is produced at a high rate. However, at longer immersion times, the corrosion layer formation inhibits the solution from reaching the substrate and its intermetallic phases and lowers the hydrogen formation. Hence, it is evident that the oxide layer corrosion behaviour changes with immersion time. Despite the short-term results, the 5V and 6V samples perform better against corrosion over long periods.

3.1.5. Surface analysis after PBS immersion

Fig. 12 shows the surface of samples immersed in PBS for 144 h after removing the corrosion products. There are left traces of the removed products on the surface, which have protected the samples against corrosion. These products were formed on the surface when samples were immersed in PBS. The extent of these products was greater for the 5V samples, for which the corrosion layers took longer to be removed. According to these Figures, despite the WE43 sample that has undergone pitting and the surface appearing generally corroded, the surfaces of the al-treated samples are reasonably well protected against corrosion as it is seen that corrosion sites on these samples are less superficial. These images illustrate that the oxide layer protected the surfaces before any layer formed following immersion in PBS [30]. Therefore, the anodic layer acts against corrosion during the initial hours of immersion to protect the surface and reduce hydrogen formation.

Fig. 11. (a) OCP of different samples versus Ag/AgCl electrode and (b) Cumulative hydrogen evolved from the surface of different samples immersed in PBS solution.

Fig. 12. SEM images of the corroded surface of the a) WE43 and Al-treated samples at b) 4 V, c) 5 V, and d) 6 V after 144 h of immersion in PBS solution.

Fig. 13. XPS spectra of the corrosion products formed on the surface of Al-treated samples after 144 h immersion in PBS solution. (a) Mg 2s, (b) P 2p, (c) C 1s, (d) Ca 2p, (e) O 1s and (f) Na 1s.

Table 6

Mass concentration (%) of XPS spectra from the surface of al-treated samples.

Sample	Mg 2s	P 2p	C 1s	Ca 2p	O 1s	Na 1s
4V	15.15	15.02	10.58	8.09	45.22	4.73
5V	13.36	15.26	10.57	8.40	45.23	7.08
6V	12.32	14.94	11.48	7.51	44.11	9.21

Fig. 14. The contact angle for WE43, al-treated, SA spray-coated, and SA dip-coated samples.

To better investigate the surface, XPS analysis was performed. Fig. 13 shows the XPS spectra of the corrosion products along with the fitted XPS results shown in Table 6, where oxygen is the most abundant element on the surface. The O 1s peak could be resolved into two spectra with peaks attributed to the presence of $\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2$ and CO_3^{2-} species [31]. The phosphorus detected at 133.2 eV can be in the form of phosphate on the surface [32], and the C 1s peak confirmed the presence of carbonate at 284.2 eV, where there are peaks that correspond to adventitious carbon and the possibility of C–O groups being present [33]. It is known that HPO_4^{2-} ions can decrease the corrosion rate of magnesium alloys, and pitting corrosion can be significantly delayed due to the precipitation of magnesium phosphate [34]. According to the results in Table 6, increasing the potential is associated with forming higher mass concentrations of carbonates, phosphates, etc., on the surface. This is the crucial reason for the better corrosion-resistant properties of the 5V and 6V samples at more extended periods. The porous microstructure absorbs these phases from the PBS, which seals the surface to act as a blockage resulting in less corrosion.

Fig. 15. SEM images of (a) al-treated, (b) SC, and (c) DC samples, showing the different microstructure and coverage of formed SA on the anodic layer by different methods.

3.2. Stearic acid treatment

3.2.1. Surface wettability and roughness

The contact angle of al-treated samples is in the range of 10–20°. This is because the porous microstructure absorbs water. To achieve a hydrophobic surface, in order to decrease PBS uptake, the stearic acid layer was coated on the surface of the 5V sample using two different methods: spray coating (SC) and dip coating (DC). Fig. 14 illustrates that the contact angle has increased significantly after forming a SA layer on the surface. The microstructure of the al-treated and SA-coated samples is shown in Fig. 15. After sealing the surface of the anodic layer with SA, the contact angle increased significantly, turning the surface hydrophobic due to the fatty nature of the SA. The nanosized pores on the SA layer formed by both SC and DC methods are seen in Fig. 16. These nanopores are formed after ethanol is evaporated from the surface. The concentration of these nanopores can affect hydrophilicity: fewer nanopores are believed to be the reason for a higher contact angle, as they can absorb water. Thus, the contact angle can be optimized using different methods and parameters.

EDS analysis (Table 7) shows that 75% of the DC sample's surface consists of carbon and only 20% oxygen due to the anodic layer below it and only 5% Mg. This means good sealing of the anodic layer (Fig. 15 (c)). For the SC sample, the surface is mostly the anodic layer. The micro-sized particles formed by spray coating are not homogeneously distributed on the surface, and even though they make the surface hydrophobic, they cannot seal the anodic layer.

3.2.2. PBS immersion

Although SA spray coating does not have a noticeable effect on the corrosion resistance of the WE43, the SA layer formed by dip coating significantly increases corrosion resistance. As shown in Fig. 17, there is a big capacitive loop for the DC samples compared to others. This means the SA layer can individually act as a barrier against corrosion if it uniformly covers the surface. The corrosion resistance associated with the SA is far greater than the increased corrosion resistance due to al-treatment. It appears that the SA layer prevents the PBS solution from penetrating the Mg substrate and could seal the anodic layer, as observed in Fig. 18. The SA layer formed by DC remains on the surface after 144 h of immersion, with slight deterioration protecting the surface against corrosion.

4. Conclusion

After alkali and SA treatments, the modified surface of the WE43 showed better adhesion, less hydrophilicity and good corrosion resistance. The main goal was less corrosion and hydrogen gas formation so the surface could maintain polymer coatings. All in all, the following conclusions can be drawn:

Fig. 16. Microstructure of SA layer formed by (a) spray coating and (b) dip coating.

Table 7
EDS analysis of a 60- μm square surface of different samples.

Sample	Element	Weight%	Atomic %
Al-treated	Mg	46.23	35.76
	O	51.14	60.11
	C	2.63	4.12
SC	Mg	46.23	35.76
	O	50.52	59.06
	C	3.65	5.68
DC	Mg	8.30	4.57
	O	24.59	20.59
	C	67.10	74.83

Fig. 17. Nyquist plot obtained after 2 h of immersion in PBS solution for different samples.

- The barrier-type anodic layer can only resist at the initial stages of immersion. However, despite its higher hydrophilicity, a porous oxide layer can protect the surface over long periods to keep the WE43 surface intact before any corrosion products layer.
- Anodic layer formed at any potential in a range of 4–6 V served to accelerate the formation of protective phases, such as phosphates from PBS immersion, that sat on the surface, helping to protect the surface against corrosion. This reduced the amount of hydrogen production before there were any corrosion products.
- Anodic layer formed at 5V exhibited good anti-corrosion behaviour over short and long periods: This is because this potential seemed appropriate for having a porous oxide layer along with an intact barrier layer as higher potentials destroy the barrier layer as the porous layer thickens both upward and downward. Thus, the potential must be controlled to have both anodic layer types on the surface for better properties.
- SA layer significantly decreased the hydrophilicity of the oxide layer and, eventually, the PBS uptake, acting as an additional barrier to corrosion. SA with good coverage sealed the anodic layer increasing corrosion resistance up to 15 times bigger.

The subsequent work will consider the samples prepared in this study for coating. Hyperbranched macromolecular cluster (HMMC) and polyplex will be used as gene-bearing layers, and different properties such as adhesion, protection, and controlled gene release will be investigated. The gene-coated WE43 will be examined in vitro for optimum gene release, biocompatibility, and degradation.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Seyed Masih Mousavizadeh: Conceptualization, Methodology, Characterization, Writing – original draft. **Zhonglei He:** Writing – review & editing. **Xiaoyu Wang:** Writing – review & editing. **Pingping Shen:** Writing – review & editing. **Wenxin Wang:** Writing – review & editing. **Michael D. Gilchrist:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition. **Nan Zhang:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition.

Fig. 18. SEM images of (a) 5V, (b) SC, and (c) DC samples after 144 h of immersion in PBS solution.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Nan Zhang reports was provided by University College Dublin.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

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